

STUDY OF GAMMA IRRADIATION AND HIGH-TEMPERATURE OXIDATION BEHAVIOR IN NANO SiB₆ MATERIAL

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Silicon boride (SiB_n) is a crystal structure formed from a binary combination of silicon (Si) and boron (B) atoms [1]. The concentration of boron in this structure is generally described as SiB_n, indicating its presence in varying amounts. SiB_n exhibits high hardness, thermal stability, and high resistance to oxidation due to its physical properties [2]. In silicon boride, which belongs to the p-type semiconductor class, each boron atom forms three covalent bonds with silicon atoms [3]. This characteristic is widely utilized for semiconductor control of electrical properties. As a semiconductor, silicon boride is extensively used in the production of electronic devices. The expected behavior of SiB_n materials, particularly in recording gamma quanta at elevated temperatures in nuclear technological facilities, is of significant interest. Additionally, the effect of the concentration of oxygen atoms captured by the active surface of nano sized SiB_n crystals on the control of the material's electrical properties has been investigated. Depending on the temperature, transitions of SiB₃, SiB₆, and SiB_n are observed in the Si-B phase diagram. As the boron concentration in the SiB matrix increases, the transitions SiB₃+Si, SiB₃+SiB₆, SiB₆+SiB_n, and SiB_n continue up to 2000°C. In this research work, the gamma irradiation and high temperature oxidation behaviors of nano SiB₆ material were studied.

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